

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-3, JUNE 2025

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ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Social Alienation to Self-destruction: A Marxian Analysis of *The End of Eddy*

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Article History: Submitted-31/05/2025, Revised-18/06/2025, Accepted-24/06/2025, Published-30/06/2025.

Abstract:

In this paper, we analyse the novel *The End of Eddy* by Édouard Louis in the light of Karl Marx's theory of alienation, which explains the estrangement of individuals from their work, their worldviews, and their sense of self. This analysis aims to highlight how social disparities affect individuals and shape their responses to discrimination within society, and how the continuous disparity is perpetuated by capitalism. The paper explores how social alienation leads a person down a path of self-destruction and sabotage, often resulting in them spiralling out of control and succumbing to depression. Furthermore, it examines how the unwritten rules that govern the functioning of society pressure so-called rebels into conforming to dominant ideals.

Keywords: Social Alienation, Self-destruction, Capitalism, Social issues, Consciousness.

Introduction:

“I am separated from all things by a hollow space, and I do not even reach to its boundaries.” This quote precisely captures the innermost feelings of a person who is distanced

from fulfilling the essential human need for social connection. The idea reflects how colonisers viewed other customs as barbaric, how individuals from lower castes face discrimination based on their social ranking, and how a person can feel like an outsider even within a seemingly cohesive group. This condition—the painful experience of being different from dominant or mainstream norms—and the desperate longing to overcome such alienation, is central to Marx's *Theory of Alienation*.

Its footprints are evident in literature, art, and culture, which serve as the vocal cords of society. The theme of self-harm, for instance, is present in the works of writers like Hemingway and Kafka. In Hemingway's *The Sun Also Rises*, the characters avoid confronting their trauma and insecurities, trapping themselves in a cycle of self-destructive behaviours. This study highlights further instances from the literature where such themes emerge. Alienation often precedes self-harm, which literature treats as a symptom of deeper social issues.

Theory of Alienation:

The Theory of Alienation, or Social Exclusion, claims that individuals or groups can be systematically denied access to resources, opportunities, and social participation based on factors such as race, class, gender, or other social characteristics. This leads to marginalisation and a lack of integration into the mainstream social, economic, and political life.

The Theory of Alienation has gone through various developmental stages across different contexts over time. It was first developed by the German idealist Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel in a philosophical sense through his work *The Phenomenology of Spirit*. According to Hegel, alienation is a stage in the development of human consciousness and self-realisation. Another important contributor to this theory was the German anthropologist and philosopher Ludwig Feuerbach, who addressed alienation in the context of religion. The theory

was significantly expanded by Karl Marx, who applied it more deeply to social and economic contexts. After Marx's death, the theory gained popularity through the works of thinkers such as Herbert Marcuse and Erich Fromm. It was embraced by existentialists, who integrated the concept of alienation into their ideas of freedom and meaning. Later, the Theory of Alienation attracted wider attention and influenced labour movements, socialist ideologies, and countercultural movements of the 1960s.

According to Marx, alienation is a profound sense of disconnection where an individual feels that they do not belong and are separated from their work, other people, their sense of self, and the products of their labour. The Theory of Alienation directly addresses the concept of class conflict by highlighting how the capitalist system inherently excludes the working class (proletariat) from full participation in society. This exclusion occurs by denying them control over the means of production, which leads to their alienation and marginalisation and effectively excludes them from the benefits of society. Such exclusion is considered a key driver of social unrest and a catalyst for potential revolutionary change.

Class is a fundamental factor in this framework, defined by one's relationship to the means of production. The working class is systematically oppressed by the capitalist class, who extracts surplus value from their labour, thereby deepening their marginalisation. Workers are alienated from the products they create, as they lack agency in the production process, which contributes to a deeper sense of exclusion and dehumanisation. Marx believed that the working class could overcome this exclusion through collective action and revolution, ultimately dismantling the capitalist system and establishing a classless society.

Social exclusion also encompasses alienation from others and one's humanity, often referred to as self-alienation. These dimensions are explored in the novel, illustrating how

societal expectations and restrictive norms suppress individual expression and hinder the realisation of personal potential.

Social Alienation as seen in *The End of Eddy*:

In *The End of Eddy*, Edouard Louis presents the lived reality of Eddy Bellegueule, a child from a working-class family in northern France, who is trapped in the void of his existence—alienated from his friends, family, and even his sense of self. Estranged from his thoughts and emotions, and raised in a society that promotes toxic masculine ideals, Eddy remains the odd one out in every social circle he enters. Masculine values are deeply embedded in the mindset of the villagers, as seen in the line: “In a world where masculine values are held up as supreme, even my mother would say about herself: ‘I have got balls, nobody messes with me’” (Louis, p. 18).

Eddy is raised in an environment where the model of masculinity includes riding mopeds, engaging in fights, playing football, excessive drinking, and even being caught by the police—activities celebrated as marks of pride. The concept of being a 'real man' or a 'tough guy' is so essential that failure to live up to these ideals results in being labelled an outcast. More than just exclusion, such deviation makes one a constant target of ridicule and contempt. Even the name *Bellegueule*, meaning 'pretty mug' or 'pretty face' in harsh slang, chosen by his father, reflects the expectation that Eddy would become a tough man, adhering to local standards.

However, Eddy grows up to be distinctly different from other boys in the village. This difference subjects him to verbal abuse and a range of homophobic slurs, including: “Faggot, fag, fairy, cocksucker, punk, pansy, sissy, wimp, girly boy, pussy, bitch, homo, fruit, poof, queer or homosexual, gayboy” (Louis, p. 8).

These insults are only part of the daily humiliation he experiences. His mannerisms—much like how capitalist structures frown upon individual creativity—are rejected by those around him. He becomes a source of amusement, a figure mocked for his difference. Louis writes, “My parents referred to my fancy ways: ‘Stop putting on those fancy ways,’ they would say to me. They would ask themselves, ‘Why does Eddy always act like such a girl?’ They would tell me insistently: ‘Calm down, cannot you lose the queeny gestures?’” (Louis, p. 15). He adds, “It was not unusual for me to hear someone say, ‘That Bellegueule kid is a little weird,’ or to be smirked at when I spoke to people” (Louis, p. 20).

These words and reactions slowly push Eddy toward what Karl Marx defines as social alienation. Rejected by his society and distanced from his identity, Eddy begins to spiral toward self-destruction, a tragic consequence of being different in a society that demands conformity.

Social Alienation from the Process and Product They Produce:

The Theory of Alienation by Karl Marx describes how capitalism isolates individuals from their work, the products they create, and even their sense of self. Due to the structure of capitalism, people become disconnected or estranged from their human nature. In *The End of Eddy*, Eddy’s parents, who belong to the working class like most others in the village, are subjected to the dominance of capitalism. The isolation caused by this system is reflected in the character of Eddy’s father. Like every other man in the village, he works in a factory. He experiences social alienation from the products he helps manufacture, as he cannot afford to buy them, leaving him powerless in this regard. Given the demanding work hours and the limited control he has over his job, he, like the other men, becomes alienated from the work process itself. The labour is mechanical and uninspiring, with survival being the only motivation. As his body deteriorates due to injury, specifically a back problem, he is left with chronic pain that follows him throughout life. Capitalism overlooks the physical and mental

well-being of its workers, reducing them to mere statistics, treated as expendable rather than as human beings. In a consumerist society dominated by capitalism, it is essential to prioritise the health and dignity of those who sustain the system, rather than masking their exploitation. This supports Marx's argument that capitalism exploits workers for profit while giving them little or nothing in return. The line, "Us little folks are nobodies, especially to the fat cats" (p. 5), summarises the condition of the working class under capitalism. The repetitive, mechanical nature of capitalist life is further reflected in the school system in Eddy's village. The school and the factory resemble each other so closely that the difference between them becomes almost imperceptible. Most children, especially those identified as tough, drop out and join the factory directly. The physical proximity of the school to the factory signifies how institutions that should nurture personal growth and self-discovery instead function as extensions of the capitalist machine. The monotonous design of the buildings, with identical red bricks and sheet metal, symbolises the absence of creativity and innovation. The same individuals remain in the same space throughout their lives, reinforcing the cycle. The education system, rather than liberating young minds to pursue their aspirations, becomes a factory in itself, mass-producing future workers. This structure ensures that the next generation remains bound to the same capitalist framework. The institution operates on the idea that people should be educated just enough to serve as obedient workers but never empowered enough to challenge the system. Eddy's innocent questions about his future are met with answers that all point in one direction: the factory. The fate of every man born in the village is seemingly predetermined by this inanimate, oppressive structure that feeds on the labour of its people. This is evident in the conversation Eddy has with his mother, highlighting how deeply entrenched the factory is in the collective psyche of the village. Thus, the capitalist system functions by stripping workers of ownership over their labour, suppressing creativity and self-expression, and keeping them bound to a system that benefits only a select few.

Alienation from Other People:

The next type of alienation that Marx outlines is alienation from other people. Eddy, who is different from other children in his village, is a regular target because of his mannerisms and interests. He faces humiliation from his peers and the villagers for being different. This results in his being treated differently, to the extent that he becomes an object of mockery and, on some occasions, dehumanisation. He is spat in the face by someone he describes as a tall boy with red hair in the hallway, along with a short boy with a hunchback. Both are senior students who take part in this act. They grab his hair while verbally harassing him with the same relentless sing-song of abuse: faggot, cocksucker. Dizziness, along with the fear of making them even angrier, forces him to hold back his tears. However, what hurts him most is their ability to quickly forget him and move on, while he devotes all his thoughts and anguish to them from the moment he wakes up. Eddy's preferences contrast sharply with what boys in his village typically enjoy. His tastes naturally turn towards the feminine, without him understanding why. He is fascinated by theatre, female vocalists, and dolls, whereas his brothers, and even his sisters in their own way, prefer video games, rap, and football. Another instance of humiliation includes the following:

“One day in the playground, Maxime, a different Maxime, asked me to run, there in front of him and the boys he was with. He said to them *Just watch how he runs like a fairy* assuring them, swearing, that they were going to have a good laugh. After I refused, he made it clear that I didn't have any choice. If I didn't do as I was told, I would pay for it *I'll punch your face in if you don't*. So, I ran for them, humiliated, fighting back tears, feeling as if each leg weighted hundreds of kilos, as if each step would be my last, they were so heavy, like the legs of someone running against the current in a rough sea. They laughed.” (Pg: 23-24)

Eddy, in the eyes of his peers, was more of an object to be ridiculed than a human being. He tried to make friends at college, but his efforts were in vain. From the moment he started college, he spent time in the playground every day trying to make friends with other students. None of them spoke to him. The stigma was contagious, and the idea of being friends with a fag was considered unacceptable. The fear he experienced is reflected in these lines, “Their faces engraved themselves in my thoughts and inexorably, the more the details – their noses, their mouth, their eyes-escaped me. All that remained was my fear.” (Pg 48). The incident in the neighbour’s shed, where he was used as a sexual object for the satisfaction of others, brings out the idea of objectification. They attempted to imitate scenes they had seen in pornographic films. He, always forced into the role of the woman, was constantly used by his friends. When the story spread, he alone became the target of taunts, not the others. His cousin shared a distorted version of the story, but it matched the image others already had of him.

As Eddy grew up, his mannerisms began to bring shame to his family. Those around him attempted to correct his behaviour. His brother, while walking with him to the bakery, spent the entire time trying to teach him how to walk properly like a real boy. His brother’s reactions to Eddy’s mannerisms and his tastes, which leaned toward the feminine, clearly reveal his disgust. He did not want to endure the shame he would feel if his friends saw him with Eddy.

When Eddy and his father met the president of the football league, whom they called Coach Cigar, Eddy witnessed the shame his father felt. When asked why Eddy had stopped attending practice, his father only mumbled a response. The shame of being confronted publicly was felt strongly during that moment.

The loneliness Eddy experienced led him to have painful thoughts reflecting the shame he believed he brought upon his family. He often imagined his family abandoning him. He

imagined that one day his mother would disappear, leaving behind a note on the table explaining her frustration with a son like him, that she had had enough of this life and was choosing to forsake him. On other days, he envisioned his parents driving him to the edge of a road or the middle of a forest and leaving him there, alone, as people sometimes did with animals. Though he knew this would likely never happen, the loneliness he felt was enough to plant that thought in his mind.

This illustrates how alienation not only leads to loneliness but also turns individuals into targets. It shows the cost of being different, how contradictions to societal norms make one more vulnerable to attack. These incidents portray the heartbreaking and tragic situation a person can face.

Alienation Faced by Other Characters or Groups:

Alienation from one's community is not limited to Eddy; it also affects women who remain unmarried or childless beyond a certain age, as they are frequently frowned upon by other women in the village. Rigid social constructs dictate that women must fulfil specific duties within a socially sanctioned time frame, according to unwritten societal expectations. If a woman fails to meet these expectations, she is presumed to have some underlying issue.

In the village, motherhood is a fundamental means through which women affirm their identity as women, primarily because they are offered no viable alternatives. If they choose not to bear children, they are often labelled as lesbians or regarded as frigid. Such women become the subject of gossip among other women, particularly outside the school gates when the children have left. These discussions often revolve around speculative assumptions, especially about the supposed lack of sexual activity in such women's lives—assumptions that are largely unfounded and intrusive.

Women are also alienated from their femininity in a toxically masculine environment. This is exemplified by the words of Eddy's mother, who declares, "I've got balls, and no one's going to mess with me"—a phrase typically associated with masculinity. Her assertion reflects how even women, to assert strength in a patriarchal setting, feel compelled to adopt the language and symbolism of male dominance, further distancing themselves from traditional expressions of femininity.

Alienation is not limited to the character of Eddy but extends to broader societal perceptions, particularly toward other races and those perceived as competitors for limited resources. Virtuous ideals often collapse in the face of competition: "...she would not hesitate to invoke those same powers she otherwise so hated when she felt ruthlessness was called for: ruthlessness in dealing with Arabs, with alcohol, with drugs, with any kind of sexual behaviour she disapproved of. She would often remark, 'What we need is some law and order in this country.'" (p. 46). These lines reflect how capitalism promotes competition over cooperation, fostering division between individuals and keeping them preoccupied with antagonism rather than unity.

The resentment directed at their neighbours further illustrates how this division manifests. His mother, like others in the village, scorns their impoverished neighbours who live in poorly constructed, unkempt homes. These individuals are labelled as "slackers" or "freeloaders," considered unproductive members of society. The derogatory portrayal of these people demonstrates how they are alienated by their own community, and how social hierarchies are constructed to elevate oneself by demeaning others. This attitude is clearly encapsulated in the following statement: "Something else my mother was always repeating, with pride: Being poor does not mean you cannot be clean, we may not have much money but the house is clean and my kid's clothes smell fresh, they are not dressed in filthy rags." (pp. 78–79).

This perspective underscores how alienation is reinforced through moral superiority and class judgment, showing that societal values shaped by capitalism lead to internal divisions that perpetuate inequality and social exclusion.

A different scenario where this aspect of traditional social alienation comes into play is in the case of the character Laura, a city girl whose background immediately set her apart from the other children at school. Laura, who had gained a bad reputation among her peers simply because she and her mother had once lived in the city, provoked hostile reactions upon arriving in the village. The way they spoke, their lifestyle, and even the clothes they wore shocked the rural community, making them targets of ridicule and exclusion. A child from such a background inevitably attracted derogatory remarks from the village children, highlighting the deep-seated class-based alienation embedded in rural life.

This alienation extended beyond appearances and behaviour; it also touched the realm of personal aspirations. Sabrina, Eddy's final attempt at love, shared her dream of becoming a doctor, an ambition far outside the norm in a community where the highest aspiration for women was often becoming a nurse's aide, a job considered menial and widely accepted by most women in the village. This contrast illustrates how class expectations stifle dreams that might otherwise liberate individuals. In order to fit in, many are forced to abandon their ambitions, thereby limiting the realization of their true potential.

The village itself stands as a symbol of isolation, seemingly frozen in time, with its residents leading lives marked by repetition and conformity, cut off from the evolving world beyond.

Alienation from One's Self:

In this form of alienation, alienation from one's humanity, the price one pays is the loss of one's sense of self. The novel presents several instances in which Eddy experiences this

state, hating himself for being born the way he is, largely due to how others treat him. The episodes of cross-dressing followed by deep disgust serve as powerful examples of his self-alienation. He feels drawn to secretly take his sister's clothes and parade around in private, purely for his pleasure. He wears everything from short skirts and clingy T-shirts to lace bras.

Eddy is the sole spectator of these performances, which, as previously mentioned, bring him genuine delight. In these moments, his euphoria overwhelms him, and he weeps tears of joy. His heart seems to burst with happiness, momentarily freeing him from the burden of shame imposed by society.

The performance leaves Eddy exhausted and increasingly disgusted with himself, stunned by the momentary lapse of reason that led him to cross-dress. It resembled those days when inebriation and disinhibition result in foolish behaviours, only to be regretted once the alcohol wears off and nothing remains but a painful and shameful memory. He would imagine cutting the clothes into pieces, burning them, and burying them in some hidden place where no one would ever find them. This self-directed disgust compelled Eddy to ensure that his younger brother, Rudy, would not follow the same path. He wanted to shield Rudy from suffering at the hands of school bullies. Determined to shape Rudy into someone who would be accepted, Eddy attempted to prepare him from a very young age. Rudy was taught to despise homosexuality; it was portrayed to him as inherently sick and as a source of damnation and disease. The idea of becoming a "tough guy" gradually took root in Eddy's mind—an identity he believed would make him like everyone else, accepted and respected. He would often repeat an obsessive phrase to himself: "*Today I am going to be a tough guy*" (p. 170). He consciously suppressed his gestures to appear more masculine, shoving his hands into his pockets to prevent them from moving freely. Despite his efforts, he realised that he felt no physical attraction toward women. To mask his insecurities, he committed himself to traditionally masculine interests: he watched football attentively, memorised the names of every player on the French team, and began

watching wrestling, just like his brothers and father. He also openly mocked gay people to deflect suspicion. This internalised homophobia became particularly evident when he began to hate another boy, even more effeminate than himself. On one occasion, when that boy was being loud in a crowded hallway, Eddy silenced him by calling him a “faggot”—a common slur used to target gay individuals—prompting laughter from the surrounding students. In that brief moment, Eddy managed to project some of the shame he had carried his entire life onto someone else through a single public insult. The hatred Eddy harboured toward his own identity was redirected toward someone who mirrored who he truly was. A root cause of his alienation was his inability to understand the origin of his traits, which led him to question his own identity. He fantasised about receiving coaching on how to control his voice, how to walk, and how to meet other people's gazes. His desperation to escape from himself was unmistakable. Even genuine expressions of surprise from others disturbed him. Such reactions made his throat tighten and his stomach twist into knots. When people asked questions like, “*Why do you talk that way?*” he would pretend not to understand, overcome by a powerful urge to scream. His sobs fought to escape, trapped in a silence filled with shame and pain.

Judith Butler’s theory of performativity is evident here, as it emphasizes that gender is not innate but constructed through repeated actions that produce socially acceptable behaviours. Eddy attempts to conform to these gender norms, performing an identity that does not reflect his true self, simply to gain acceptance within society.

Just as Marx explains in his theory, instead of resisting the system, Eddy becomes a victim of social aggression and violence. He develops self-hatred due to imposed masculine ideals and internalises shame about his working-class background, which fuels his desire to escape his hometown. This act of escape serves as a form of resistance—an attempt by Eddy to break free from the path of self-destruction.

Self-Destruction as a Possibility:

In the novel, Eddy also temporarily falls into the trap of self-destruction. At times, he expresses hatred toward gay people, which is a projection of his own self-loathing. He feels disgusted with himself for cross-dressing and even imagines burning the clothes—an act symbolising a desire to erase his own identity and mode of existence. His efforts to change himself to conform to societal stereotypes can be understood as forms of self-destructive behaviour. Ultimately, he decides to escape the village that saves him from this destructive cycle.

Once all means of seeking help are exhausted, individuals may resort to self-harm. In such cases, society often adopts a regressive stance. Apathy from the general public reinforces this mindset and contributes to the perpetuation of self-destructive behaviour.

Prevailing social structures often emerge from unresolved societal gaps. By leaving these flaws and problems behind, society inadvertently incorporates them into modern institutions that arise from such structures. The novel highlights how the presence of these seemingly indelible flaws undermines the very foundation of society. This continued ignorance or negligence obstructs the development of an inclusive social framework—one that can promote effective administration and governance, supported by a just legal system that protects the rights of marginalised individuals. Such reform is essential for achieving equitable and sustainable outcomes.

Outcome of Social Alienation:

A person leading an alienated existence is more likely to experience mental health deterioration, ultimately raising questions about their own identity and purpose. Such individuals often struggle to build and maintain meaningful relationships with others. Those

who exhibit antisocial behaviour frequently have a history of social abandonment and lack the emotional support necessary for healthy psychological development.

In *The Bell Jar* by Sylvia Plath, the protagonist, Esther Greenwood, experiences mental instability and suicidal tendencies, serving as an example of a person who engages in self-destructive behaviour.

In Graham Greene's novel *The Heart of the Matter*, the protagonist, Henry Scobie, commits suicide due to his unhappy marriage, toxic work environment, and several other contributing factors. Ultimately, the cumulative emotional distress proved unbearable for him.

Relevance of this Study:

It is crucial to examine the underlying patterns and psychological trends that contribute to self-destructive behaviour to prevent such potentially fatal outcomes. One of the key solutions is to educate children to respect and value each other's differences. It is equally important to help them understand the reasons behind these differences, so they do not internalise feelings of inferiority or develop self-hatred. Such moral values about compassion and acceptance should be promoted for understanding their self and their potential, which would develop better human beings. Such initiatives are essential to dismantle the hierarchical mindset that society holds toward individuals based on their economic background. By challenging these biases, we can foster genuine human connections and promote a more inclusive and compassionate social fabric, ultimately uniting humanity.

Conclusion:

This study seeks to interpret self-destructive tendencies as portrayed in literature and their parallels in real-life psychological experiences, highlighting how timely identification and intervention may avert profound personal and societal crises. It aims to serve as a critical reminder to society of the ethical imperative to extend empathy and support to individuals

grappling with inner turmoil. Rather than relegating them to isolation or neglect, society must recognize their inherent potential and strive to nurture the resilience and creative spirit that often lie dormant within.

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